

LinearWorks:

Enhancing industrial quality control
with AI and hyperspectral imaging

Innovate
UK

BridgeAI

CASE STUDY

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Founded by pioneers in artificial intelligence, earth observation, and supply chain management, [LinearWorks](#) utilises hyperspectral imaging (HSI) and artificial intelligence to address complex challenges across various industries. Its technology assists agricultural stakeholders in crop monitoring and management and allows verification of the safety and durability of building materials. Although the company's initial focus was on agriculture, it has expanded into sectors such as construction by adapting HSI-based technology to detect subtle material defects that conventional inspection methods often overlook.

To support this strategic shift, LinearWorks participated in the Independent Scientific Advisor (ISA) programme under Innovate UK's BridgeAI initiative. Through this programme, the company worked with Dr Kit Windows-Yule, an artificial intelligence expert from the University of Birmingham and The Alan Turing Institute, who provided valuable feedback on strategic direction and funding proposals.

A later funding opportunity involved working with a concrete manufacturer. LinearWorks installed HSI cameras on the production line to assess quality and detect irregularities in prefabricated concrete using bespoke algorithms. The goals were to enhance quality control during curing and to create a digital audit trail, allowing manufacturers to demonstrate compliance with required standards.

"Kit's support has been instrumental in shaping how we communicate our ideas to academic and government funders," says Chris Felder, CEO of LinearWorks. "Coming from an industry background, it is a different way of thinking. Kit helped translate our vision into something that academic reviewers would understand – and that directly contributed to us winning two grants last year. The company has filed a UK patent for its HSI technology and continues to grow and lead the way in HSI technology."

LinearWorks' participation in BridgeAI also brought the opportunity to lead one of the Turing's Mini Data Study Groups, where they posed a challenge to early-career AI and data science researchers focused on using HSI to detect defects in materials under changeable environmental conditions. "We were able to work with a group of PhD students who brought fresh energy and ideas," says Chris. "They came at the challenge from all sorts of different angles, both technical and practical. We talked about protecting our HSI cameras from dust in a live production environment, compensating for lighting changes, and improving the system's overall robustness. It really made us think differently about how we could deploy the technology."

Insights from the Mini Data Study Group – particularly around the diverse applications of the company's HSI technology – helped LinearWorks recognise the need to separate its business streams. This led to the creation of LinearLabs, a dedicated company arm focused on global supply chain solutions, including the tracking and monitoring of temperature-controlled assets. Chris adds: "LinearLabs is where experimentation meets execution. We're a research-driven innovation lab focused on designing intelligent systems that respond to the real world in real time. Our work blends AI, remote sensing, simulation and systems thinking to help industries adapt faster, operate smarter, and unlock new frontiers of value."

Chris Felder, CEO, LinearWorks

"BridgeAI's support has been instrumental for LinearWorks. Through the ISA program and Mini Data Study Group, we gained invaluable opportunities for strategic reflection and business repositioning. The collaborative support from BridgeAI and its network of partner organisations has delivered concrete, enduring value that continues to influence our growth and success."

Chris Felder,
CEO, LinearWorks

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About Innovate UK BridgeAI

Innovate UK BridgeAI empowers UK businesses in high-growth sectors, driving productivity and economic growth through the adoption of Artificial Intelligence. We bridge the gap between developers and end-users, fostering user-driven AI technologies.

With a focus on ethics, transparency and data privacy, we aim to build trust and confidence in the development of AI solutions. Strengthening AI leadership, supporting workforces, and promoting responsible innovation, BridgeAI shapes a collaborative and AI-enabled future.

BridgeAI is an Innovate UK funded programme, delivered by a consortium including Innovate UK, Digital Catapult, The Alan Turing Institute, STFC Hartree and BSI.

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